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Experiences of Marital Strain in Joint Families and Its Psychological and Emotional Effects on Married Couples

Abstract

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The present study was designed to explore the psychological and emotional impact of marital strain on married couples in the joint family system in Sargodha Division, Pakistan. Joint families have often been cherished for their role in providing mutual support and social order but can also create marital issues in terms of in-law interference, lack of privacy, unequal domestic responsibilities, as well as decreased autonomy of couples. A qualitative phenomenological design was used, and 48 participants (24 married

teacher couples) were interviewed, who had an average of at least three years of marriage. Theme analysis showed that marital strain led to psychological problems such as stress, anxiety, sleeping difficulties and decreased attention span, and emotional problems such as tiredness, loneliness, resentment, anger and lower marital satisfaction. The emotional and domestic responsibilities were found to be more onerous for the female, and the balance amongst parental expectations and spouse's demands was

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noted as one of the difficulties faced by the males. The use of coping skills (silence, patience, prayer and setting boundaries) was only temporary. The study findings identify the need for culturally sensitive family counselling, better communication between couples and respecting husband and wife's privacy in the context of a joint family system to reduce the strain of a marriage.

Keywords: Marital Strain, Joint Family System, Psychological Effects, Emotional Effects, Married Couples

Note: The article has been drawn from the PhD research thesis of the first author.

1. Introduction

The joint family system plays a crucial role in the sociocultural fabric of Pakistan and is sometimes viewed as a model of unity, support, and continuity across generations. Even though it is addressed as a marvelous form of family organization, this traditional structure is an understated form of family life, where married couples must contend with multiple competing loyalties, hierarchical ordering and a restricted degree of personal autonomy within the same household. Often, the seemingly peaceful presentation of intergenerational cooperation covers up power dynamics, expectations not met, and relationship challenges that bring significant strain into marital relationships (Greenberg, 2020). This is vital not only for the betterment of the individual couple but also to enhance the social networks of the Pakistani families and communities.

Marital strain is a combination of the psychological and emotional stresses, dissatisfaction and chronic conflict that develop over time in a marriage. Long-term marital stress has been found to increase risk of clinical depression, general anxiety, psychosomatic symptoms, as well as

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marital separation in extreme cases over and over again (Garcia & Umberson, 2019). When families are living together, the sources of this strain are complex and often exacerbated by in-laws, who may have expectations and interfere with the husband/wife's interactions, further reducing satisfaction with the marriage. Lack of physical and emotional privacy also exacerbates these difficulties, hindering the growth of marital intimacy and conflict resolution (Jia, 2021).

Patriarchal norms are entrenched in the society and give women more domestic duties and less decision-making power in Pakistan. In extended family systems, the family members put the needs of other family members before their own, which can lead to emotional exhaustion and resentment on the part of women and a lack of marital satisfaction (Ahmed et al., 2022). Couples often lack independent agency because they do not have the autonomy to make decisions on issues of finances, child-rearing and household management – a decision-making process that is frequently determined by the consent of all family members (Lodhi et al., 2019). The ongoing imbalance in marital roles can create instability in relationships and psychological issues for both partners.

Although a large number of books are available on the quality of marriage and dynamics of family life in South Asia, empirical studies on the psychological and emotional consequences of marital strain in the context of joint families in Pakistan are still limited. This study aims to fill this gap by examining the lived experience of married couples in Sargodha Division who live in joint families and their psychological impact, emotional effects and coping mechanisms for coping with marital strain in this culturally specific context. The goals of the research are to provide contextually relevant and empirically informed findings that can be used for mental health

interventions, family counselling and social policies to help married couples in Pakistan.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

- To examine the psychological effects of marital strain on married couples residing in joint family systems.
- To explore the emotional effects of marital strain on married couples living in joint families.
- To identify and recommend culturally sensitive strategies for mitigating the psychological and emotional effects of marital strain within joint family contexts.

1.2 Research Questions

- What are the psychological effects of marital strain on married couples residing in joint families?
- What are the emotional effects of marital strain on married couples living in joint families?
- What strategies can effectively mitigate the psychological and emotional effects of marital strain within joint family systems?

2. Literature Review

The joint family system has been extensively studied in Pakistan as a leading social institution and its impact on individual life, gender roles and family relationship has been discussed. Though the joint family system can provide social and economic solidarity, it can also lead to tensions in the relationship, especially for women, who are exposed to multiple stressors from their spousal, parental, and extended family relationships (Lodhi et al., 2021). This review highlights the contributions from empirical and theoretical research in the arena of marital strain in the context of joint families, focusing on psychological, emotional and socio-cultural aspects.

2.1 Psychological Dimensions of Marital Strain

Studies have shown time and time again that marital quality and psychological well-being have a reciprocal relationship. Lee et al. (2020) found that psychological symptoms (depression and anxiety) are associated with problematic conflict responses in the family that in turn increase marital strain and relationship deterioration. On an individual level, several psychologic factors are responsible for the experience of marital strain in Pakistan. Husband-wife relationship satisfaction is considered as one of the major factors influencing psychological well-being and is often affected among young married women who experience low autonomy and lifelong pressure to adhere to patriarchy and socially conservative values (Li et al., 2025).

In such contexts, women tend to internalize a sense of responsibility for the marital harmony but without any of the power to have a significant impact on marital outcomes, leading to chronic psychological stress and relational dissatisfaction. In addition, Lyngdoh et al. (2023) found that poor marital adjustment, poor communication and inadequate social support were found to be significantly related to high levels of depression and anxiety among married females in Pakistan. Social support was identified as a protective factor for mental health; the lack of which intensified the negative impact of marital difficulties on women's mental health.

Intimate partner violence is a severe form of marital strain and has significant psychological impacts. Intimate partner violence including physical, psychological and sexual violence has been reported to be common in Pakistan, and was found to be negatively related to suicidal ideation, depression and anxiety among women in the study of Sardinha et al (2022). Cultural stigma and societal barriers are significant barriers to

help-seeking, and therefore to ending exposure to psychological harm. Leemis et al. (2022) emphasized that one of the causes of psychological vulnerability is the lack of communication, particularly during marital conflicts, whereby women who do not communicate openly or are withdrawn from the conflict are likely to suffer from greater psychological distress and health issues, as well as being more susceptible to mental health problems that stem from the conflict with their husbands.

2.2 Emotional Consequences and Socio-Cultural Influences

Marital strain has a strong emotional component that is deeply rooted in the socio-cultural milieu of the joint family. Emotional exhaustion has been found to be one of the major factors responsible for the emotional exhaustion of married women in Pakistan due to role overload where women are expected to perform many competing roles within the family and household (Ahmed et al., 2022). The emotional exhaustion, frustration, and resentment experienced by women towards husbands who put their extended family members' needs first can also reduce marital emotional closeness and satisfaction (Lodhi et al., 2019).

In addition to that, external factors like infertility, work-family imbalance or economical stress can increase marital stress by diminishing partners' satisfaction and emotional and sexual closeness (Pluut et al., 2022). A personal and relational aspect of experiences was highlighted, as empathy and supportive communication were seen as protective factors for the emotional effects of marital stress. These results indicate that emotional health in marriage isn't solely the result of personal resilience but would also depend on the quality of the marriage relationship and how sensitive the partners are to each other's emotional needs.

2.3 Education, Professional Resources, and Coping Mechanisms

Education and paid work are known as important psychosocial factors that can buffer the effects of marital strain. According to Latif et al., (2023) the education of the women in Pakistan is positively correlated with improved communication skills, better problem-solving skills, and better marital satisfaction. Educated women have the skills to use flexibility in family communication and to express their family life needs without using confrontational communication. Likewise, Khezri et al. (2020) showed that interventions aimed at enhancing couples' communication skills are effective in increasing marital satisfaction and decreasing psychological distress during periods of high stress.

A paradoxical situation arises from the literature, however, is that while education and financial independence provide psychological empowerment and self-confidence to the women, it does not necessarily lead to greater power to decide in patriarchal joint family system. According to Gheyassi and Alambeigi (2024), the gender power dynamics in Pakistani families are likely to perpetuate the power of men and elders in decision making, thereby restricting the degree of female empowerment in breaking the existing gender hierarchy. This has been supported by Takawira (2018) and Ngoma & Ntale (2016) who reported that although educated women have more adaptive coping mechanisms and conflict resolution skills, the family structures still limit their relationship power. The findings presented here imply that interventions to reduce marital strain should be targeted at both the individual and systemic components.

3. Research Methodology

The study used a qualitative research design of a phenomenological type to understand the lived experience of married couples facing marital stress in married families. The most suitable framework was phenomenology due to

its capacity to examine and analyze the experience of individuals in a detailed manner, as it is subjective, with a focus on how they perceive, interpret and create meaning from their experiences (Creswell & Poth, 2018). A phenomenological study was used as the epistemological basis for understanding the psychological and emotional effects of marital strain experienced by people within a culturally particular context because it was thought that this would capture the complexity, nuance and subjective reality of the participants' experiences. This approach enabled the voices and perspectives of participants to be the core of the research process and thus to yield contextually relevant and empirically rich findings. The study was carried out in Sargodha Division, Punjab province in Pakistan. The participants included 24 married couples (48 individuals) who were working in public and private schools in the division as teachers. The educational context for the teaching profession was chosen as the occupational context because of the ease with which a fairly homogeneous group could be obtained in terms of educational level and professional background for comparative analysis of marital experiences in a consistent socio-professional context. The participants were selected by purposive sampling method and were selected based on the following inclusion criteria: (a) legally married, (b) living in a joint family system and (c) having minimum three years of marital experience to give them adequate exposure to the phenomenon under study.

4. Data Analysis and Interpretation

4.1 Data Analysis Procedure

Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data to identify the psychological and emotional consequences of marital strain in married couples in joint family system. All interviews were transcribed, reviewed and coded with

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great care following data collection. The analysis was systematic and comprised familiarization with the data, initial coding, categorization, coding of similar statements into categories, elaboration of major themes and interpretation of the themes in the context of the research aims.

In the first phase, the transcripts of the interviews were read several times to gain insight into how the participants lived. During the second stage, relevant statements regarding marital strain, emotional pressure, interference of the family, emotional stress, and coping mechanisms were identified. Initial codes were then developed from these statements. Codes were then clustered into larger categories, and the larger categories, into major themes. Themes were understood within the context of research goals and literature available on marital strain, joint family systems, psychological distress, and emotional well-being. As this study was qualitative, the numbers in the tables are the number of participants who commented on an issue during the interviews. These values represent not statistical attitudes, but are indicative of the frequency and intensity of theme that emerged in the participant responses.

Table 1: *Demographic Information*

<i>Demographic Aspects</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Total participants	Married individuals	48	100%
Couples	Married couples	24	100%
Gender	Male	24	50%
Gender	Female	24	50%
Age	25–30 years	10	20.8%
Age	31–35 years	16	33.3%
Age	36–40 years	14	29.2%
Age	41 years and above	8	16.7%
Duration of marriage	3–5 years	12	25.0%
Duration of marriage	6–10 years	20	41.7%
Duration of marriage	More than 10 years	16	33.3%
Family system	Joint family	48	100%
Occupation	Public school teachers	28	58.3%
Occupation	Private school teachers	20	41.7%
Residence	Urban	30	62.5%
Residence	Rural/semi-urban	18	37.5%

From the demographic profile, it can be observed that all the participants were married people who were living in joint family system. The equal numbers of men and women participants enabled the study to compare experiences of men and women. The age of most participants (31 – 40 years) also suggests that they experienced enough marital and family experiences to have some meaningful thoughts to offer regarding marital

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strain. Most of the respondents were married for more than five years, enhancing the reliability of their responses as they have had a considerable period of experience living together as a family. Teachers from public and private schools were included giving a relatively educated sample. This was helpful because the educated participants could articulate their psychological/emotional experiences. Although all the participants underwent schooling and jobs, they still complained of low autonomy, intrusiveness of family members, emotional fatigue, and stress within the joint family system.

Table 2: Coding Framework of the Study

<i>Initial Codes</i>	<i>Categories</i>	<i>Major Themes</i>
Tension, overthinking, fear of conflict, disturbed sleep	Psychological pressure	Psychological effects of marital strain
Sadness, anger, resentment, loneliness, crying, emotional tiredness	Emotional burden	Emotional effects of marital strain
In-law interference, lack of privacy, household pressure, decision-making control	Sources of marital strain	of Joint family-related causes of strain
Silence, avoidance, patience, religious coping, talking to spouse, seeking advice	Adjustment practices	Coping strategies
Reduced communication, emotional distance, weak intimacy, lack of trust	Marital relationship problems	Impact on marital satisfaction

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Initial Codes

Pressure on women, domestic workload, elder dominance, male authority

Categories

Gendered family roles

Major Themes

Patriarchal and cultural influence

The coding framework reveals that marital strain within joint family systems is not due to just one cause. It happens in a different way, though: It comes from the psychological stress, the feeling of not being happy, the demands of the house, family interference, the division of chores, and the absence of privacy in the relationship. The themes suggest that married couples have internal marital stress and strain which is expressed as emotional pain as well as external stress and strain which is expressed as expectation and pressure within the family and society. The data also indicate that women do not have as much decision-making autonomy as men and may have higher expectations within their families, along with higher levels of household responsibilities, which could result in the feeling of marital strain. Men also feel stressed, particularly because of financial worries, the need to be responsible for the family and spouse, and the inability to control disputes within the family.

Table 3: *Major Themes Identified from Interviews*

Theme	Description	Participants Mentioning Theme
Psychological stress	Mental pressure, anxiety, overthinking, sleep disturbance	39
Emotional exhaustion	Feeling tired, emotionally drained, helpless, or unappreciated	36
In-law interference	Extended family involvement in couple matters	34
Lack of privacy	Limited personal space and lack of emotional intimacy	31
Communication problems	Avoidance, silence, arguments, misunderstanding	29
Gender role burden	Unequal domestic workload and patriarchal expectations	28
Reduced marital satisfaction	Weak emotional bonding and dissatisfaction with marriage	27
Coping through patience and silence	Avoiding conflict to maintain family peace	25
Religious and spiritual coping	Prayer, patience, reliance on faith	22
Need for boundaries	Desire for privacy, separate space, and mutual respect	21

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Psychological stress, emotional exhaustion and in-law stress were the most common themes reported. It shows that marital strain in joint family system has a high mental and emotional impact on the married couples. The participants repeatedly reported that the constant intrusion of family into personal matters led to a greater sense of misunderstanding between spouses and a decrease in the emotional intimacy between spouses. The high rate of lack of privacy also indicates that the living of a joint family may restrict the growth of marital intimacy. Most participants reported that they were not able to talk about their personal problems as other members of the family were always there. This was an emotional separation for husband and wife. The results also indicate that many couples resort to silence and patience to deal with issues, which may not address the issues but rather be suppressing them.

Table 4: *Psychological Effects of Marital Strain*

Psychological Effect	Male Participants	Female Participants	Total Participants
Stress and mental pressure	18	21	39
Anxiety and fear of conflict	14	19	33
Overthinking	15	20	35
Sleep disturbance	11	16	27
Lack of concentration at work	13	12	25
Feelings of helplessness	9	18	27

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<i>Psychological Effect</i>	<i>Male Participants</i>	<i>Female Participants</i>	<i>Total Participants</i>
<i>Low self-confidence</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>22</i>

The results indicate that marital strain has an impact on men and women. The most prevalent psychological effects were stress and mental pressure. Participants reported that there was a sense of mental fatigue as a result of frequent conflicts, family involvement and the desire to keep peace in the family. There was a higher anxiety level, overthinking, helplessness and low levels of self-confidence among the female participants than among the male participants. This could be attributed to the fact that the women in the joint families are under more domestic obligations, pressure from in-laws and less authority in the matters of decision making within the family. There were reports that many women were unable to openly voice their negative feelings as this could lead to problems with the husband's family. Male participants also mentioned psychological pressure, particularly if they were faced with the demands of parents and husband. Some men reported a sense of helplessness between being loyal to their parents, and being responsible for their wives' emotions. This role conflict led to stress, frustration and a lack of concentration at work.

Table 5: Emotional Effects of Marital Strain

<i>Emotional Effect</i>	<i>Male Participants</i>	<i>Female Participants</i>	<i>Total Participants</i>
<i>Emotional exhaustion</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>36</i>
<i>Loneliness despite living with family</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>31</i>
<i>Anger and frustration</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>35</i>

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<i>Emotional Effect</i>	<i>Male Participants</i>	<i>Female Participants</i>	<i>Total Participants</i>
<i>Resentment toward spouse or in-laws</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>31</i>
<i>Reduced emotional intimacy</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>31</i>
<i>Feeling unappreciated</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>29</i>
<i>Sadness and crying episodes</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>23</i>

The emotional results show that marital tension has a profound influence on the emotional life of marital couples. The most frequently reported impact was 'emotional exhaustion'. Participants indicated that they were tired of the endless family conflicts, home expectations, and unaddressed marital problems. Many of those who participated said that they felt they lived in a big family, but that there was a lack of emotional support. The female respondents expressed greater feelings of loneliness, resentment, sadness and feeling unappreciated. This indicates the emotional burden of playing several roles for the family and emotionally unsupported. Women sometimes believed that they were given credit for their contribution in the different roles that they played in the home, parenthood and adaptation to the family.

Anger and frustration were reported more often than sadness, by male participants. This implies that men may exhibit emotional stress in a way other than showing emotion—by becoming irritable, withdrawn or by remaining silent. Some husbands were unhappy as they could not please both parents and wife. The results indicate that emotional stress is a factor

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in reducing marital intimacy. If the couples can't communicate privately and freely, it causes a decrease in emotional intimacy. Consequently, marriage becomes a more practical than an emotional experience.

Table 6: *Main Sources of Marital Strain in Joint Families*

Source of Strain	Frequency	Interpretation
Interference of in-laws	34	Family involvement in private couple matters created conflict and misunderstanding.
Lack of privacy	31	Couples could not discuss personal issues or develop emotional closeness freely.
Unequal domestic responsibilities	28	Women carried a heavier burden of household work and caregiving.
Financial decision-making by elders	24	Couples felt restricted in making independent financial choices.
Parenting interference	22	Elders' involvement in child-rearing created disagreement between spouses.
Comparison with other family members	20	Comparisons increased jealousy, resentment, and emotional dissatisfaction.
Limited couple autonomy	29	Couples felt unable to make decisions independently.

Marital stress came primarily from in-laws interfering in the marriage. The participants described how family conflicts escalated from a minor issue to a major conflict when the family members became involved in the couple's relationship. This caused a lack of trust between the husband and wife and

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a harder time resolving conflict. A lack of privacy was also a significant cause of stress. Joint families are a kind of family where couples may live together with their parents, siblings and other relatives. This is challenging for couples to communicate effectively, individually spend time together, or privately address conflict. Lack of privacy led to emotional distance and less marital satisfaction.

There was also a strain in the household sphere because of unequal domestic responsibilities, particularly the latter being borne by women. Women respondents talked about the dual role they were expected to play, namely that of a student, homemaker, parent, and a family member. This caused emotional exhaustion and resentment due to this role overload. The results indicate that this joint family system becomes problematic when the support becomes control, interference and restriction of the autonomy of couples.

Table 7: Coping Strategies Used by Participants

Coping Strategy	Male Participants	Female Participants	Total Participants
Silence and avoidance	11	14	25
Religious coping and prayer	9	13	22
Discussion with spouse	12	10	22
Seeking advice from elders	10	8	18
Emotional withdrawal	9	11	20
Setting boundaries	8	13	21

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Coping Strategy	Male Participants	Female Participants	Total Participants
Focusing on children/work	10	12	22

The results indicate that adaptive and non-adaptive coping strategies were used. Most frequently used coping strategies were silence and avoidance. Some participants were hesitant to have direct interaction with the family due to fear of family conflict. This approach, however, tended to lead to feelings of being suppressed and to resentments. There was also a large amount of religious coping. Prayer, patience and trust in Allah were reported to help the participants to bear marital stress. It underscores the significance of culturally appropriate coping strategies of Pakistani families. Some of the participants employed healthier coping mechanisms: talking to partner, setting limits and work or kids. But, it would be tricky in joint families to set boundaries as elders know better and have different expectations. Overall, the results indicate that there is a need for couples to improve their ability to cope with marital stress through increased communication skills, privacy, emotional support and family counseling.

Table 8: Objective-Wise Summary of Findings

Research Objective	Major Finding	Interpretation
To examine psychological effects of marital strain	Stress, overthinking, disturbance, helplessness	anxiety, Marital strain negatively affects mental health and daily functioning.
To explore emotional effects of marital strain	Emotional loneliness, sadness, reduced intimacy	exhaustion, Marital strain weakens emotional connection and marital satisfaction.

<i>Research Objective</i>	<i>Major Finding</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
<i>To identify strategies for reducing strain</i>	<i>Communication, boundaries for religious coping, counseling, privacy</i>	<i>Couples need both personal coping skills and family-level support.</i>

The results presented are able to meet all the three objectives of the research. The first was achieved by the recognition of the psychological factors (stress, anxiety, overthinking, disturbance of sleep, helplessness). The second was to be achieved by the emotional response of loneliness, resentment, frustration, sadness and emotional exhaustion. The third goal was achieved through the identification of coping mechanisms and potential interventions such as couple communication, boundary setting, family counseling and culturally appropriate support systems. The overall interpretation is that marital strain in joint family is not only a marital problem but it is a family and cultural problem. Inadequate autonomy, in-law involvement, gendered expectations and the absence of privacy cause strain to couples. Hence, solutions must not only be for the couple, but should be for the broader family context as well.

4.2 Thematic Interpretation of Findings

Theme 1: Psychological Pressure and Mental Stress

Often, the participants mentioned that they were subjected to constant psychological pressures due to the marital strain. Many said that they could not get a restful night's sleep even upon returning home from their job. For many couples, the home became an emotional, even physical stressor, the place they would normally expect to find comfort and emotional safety. Some of the participants felt that they were mentally drained from repeated attempts by their families to interfere in their activities. Some

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participants have said that they find themselves thinking too much about family issues at night and this has an impact on their sleep and performance at work. This demonstrates that marital stress has a negative impact on marital functioning as well as on work and personal functioning. *I think my mind is always at home even at school I think what will be happening in the evening.*

Theme 2: Emotional Exhaustion and Loneliness

Though they reside in a joint family some participants mentioned they felt emotionally lonely. This is significant as families that are united are looked at as supportive families. The data indicate that togetherness does not necessarily develop into emotional support, however. Female participants particularly expressed emotional fatigue due to their roles to adapt, be silent and keep harmony within the family. A large number of women felt their emotional needs were not catered for. Males also mentioned emotional stress, typically in the form of frustration, and not necessarily sadness.

“There are a lot of people house, sometimes, I feel that no one understands me.”

Theme 3: In-Law Interference and Reduced Couple Autonomy

Marital strain was caused by in-law interference, one of the most salient factors. Elders were mentioned as having an impact on decisions relating to finances, children, household and day-to-day activities. This set up conflict between the husband and wife since they are not independently able to operate their marital lives. The results indicate that excessive control of family support is related to an increase in marital strain. The respect for elders is a cultural value, and if marriage partners' decisions are restricted by their elders, they are more likely to experience marital dissatisfaction.

“They have to take their family into consideration when deciding on small things.”

Theme 4: Lack of Privacy and Weak Emotional Intimacy

A lack of privacy was also a key issue in the discussions. Participants stated that it was difficult to have personal time between the husband and wife in the joint family system. Discussions of difficult personal issues were challenging for couples. Consequently, there were no resolutions to the conflicts and a lack of emotional intimacy. The interpretation implies that privacy is a tangible and also an emotional need for marital happiness. Couples can cohabit without emotional intimacy due to lack of privacy.

“Someone is always there and we are not able to talk freely as we are living in the same room together.”

Theme 5: Gendered Role Burden

The emotional and psychological burden due to domestic expectations was reported to be more by the female participants. As teachers, they had to carry out their professional responsibilities and at the same time have to deal with domestic matters. For many women their paid-up job did not lessen their domestic chores. The finding indicates that equality does not exist in joint family systems in terms of education and employment. Traditional family roles can still limit women, who are working in the professional sphere.

My second job begins after school but, of course, no one thinks I am tired at home.

Theme 6: Coping Through Silence, Patience, and Faith

Silence, patience and religious coping were used by many participants to cope with marital strain. These techniques helped to avoid open conflict and also to leave unresolved issues. Silence was a norm for family peace,

particularly applied by the women. Religious coping was found to be a mechanism that helped participants to emotionally tolerate stress. The results indicated, however, that religious coping needs to be communicated, counseled and healthy boundaries set regarding this.

I don't say anything because it will only make it worse, but I feel heavy in my heart.

5. Discussion

The present study aimed to find out psychological and emotional consequences of marital strain among the married couples in joint family system in Sargodha Division. Given the qualitative phenomenological design of the study, the discussion will highlight the common lived experiences, meanings and themes the participants shared. The study was conducted with married couples residing in joint families and selected teachers of public and private schools, Sargodha Division were educated and professionally similar to provide the understanding of the marital strain in a culturally specific family context. The results suggest that in a joint family system, the marital strain is not restricted to marital conflict. Instead, it is influenced by a broader system of family norms, in-laws, shared roles, lack of privacy, economical autonomy, parenting interference and cultural norms. The findings indicated that the joint family life can bring support, protection and responsibility to the married couples but if the family involvement is too high, it can result in psychological pressure and emotional dissatisfaction within the family.

The results of the study reveal that marital stress in joint family can have detrimental psychological and emotional effects on the married couples. The participants felt stressed, anxious, overthinking, exhausted emotionally, lonely, resentful and not satisfied in their conjugal relationships.

In-law interference, lack of privacy, unequal domestic responsibilities, limited autonomy of couples and poor communication between couples were the major causes of these effects. The outcomes additionally point to the pressure that can result from transforming family supports into family control and family interferences in joint family life. Participants found their coping mechanisms to be silence, patience, prayer, emotional withdrawal, or talking with their spouses; but, they felt that these coping strategies often didn't fully resolve marital issues and provided only temporary relief.

In general, the research indicates that marital stress is a personal stress between husband and wife, but it is also a family and culture associated stress. Hence, culturally responsive family counselling, interaction among husband and wife, establishing healthy boundaries and respecting marital privacy are crucial to alleviate psychological and emotional burden of married couples living in extended families.

6. Conclusion

The study has found that marital stress within the joint family system has a high psychological and emotional impact on the married couples. Stress, anxiety, overthinking, emotional exhaustion, loneliness, resentment and decreased marital satisfaction were reported. In-law interference, lack of privacy, unequal domestic responsibilities, lack of autonomy within the couple and poor communication were the main causes of strain. While some coping strategies included silence, patience, prayer, emotional withdrawal, and discussing with spouses, most of these strategies were short-term and their effectiveness in resolving marital tensions was limited. The study suggests that culturally sensitive family counselling, better communication between husband and wife, setting boundaries and respecting marital privacy are necessary to alleviate psychological and emotional stress of

marital strain in joint family system. Marital strain was found psychologically to be related to persistent stress, anxiety, mental fatigue, low self-esteem and identity suppression. Emotionally, it became evident as sadness, frustration, loneliness, emotional detachment and a gradual erosion of intimacy in the marriage. The impact of these was identified on marital satisfaction, participants' professional functioning, social relationships and their quality of life. Shared professional identity, effective communication, spousal support and boundary-setting were found to be protective and coping mechanisms. Importantly, although women gained access to education and professional employment, it did not consistently help to break out of unequal power structures that had been built up at the systemic level in joint family systems, suggesting the importance of a combination of systemic and individual level interventions.

Based on the summary of the study, it is concluded that marital strain in a joint family is a complicated phenomenon which needs multileveled responses for the individual psychological wellbeing, dyadic relationship issues, family-system issues and socio-cultural norms. Joint families are certainly helpful to have in Pakistan but the circumstances where they exacerbate marital conflicts should be critically reviewed and resolved so that the married couples can be healthy in this country.

7. Recommendations

In view of the results of the study, the following recommendations are made for stakeholders:

- It is important to encourage openness and honesty by married couples in relationships, and to promote constructive problem-solving in dealing with disagreements and increase emotional closeness before it becomes a habit that contributes to negative, destructive patterns.

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- *Clear interpersonal boundaries should be set in couples by mutual agreement, to uphold marital autonomy and privacy in the family while keeping the harmony and cooperation of the larger family intact.*
- *The importance of spousal space and marital privacy should be driven home to family members, especially in-laws, and should be actively encouraged by community and religious leaders to foster supportive, rather than intrusive, family dynamics.*
- *Couples' counseling and therapy services should be tailored to the unique context of joint family systems in Pakistan, culturally recognizing the experiences of marital strain from a gender perspective, and be developed and promoted by mental health professionals.*
- *The educational institutions and job providers must create programs and policies to assist the health of married teaching professionals, such as stress management training, workload management strategies and provision of employee assistance programs.*

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